

Islamic bank selection criteria in Morocco: The innovation diffusion theory perspective

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to identify the Moroccan client's choosing criteria for an Islamic bank by the innovation diffusion theory perspective. Through this exploratory study, we aim to detect the criteria taken into consideration by an Islamic bank client. Our study allowed us to detect the most influential criteria that an Islamic bank may use to set up actions and strategies to target easily potential clients who are interested in the bank Islamic products.

To answer the set problem, a survey was conducted on a random sample using the google Forms platform. Our final sample consisted of 180 questionnaires, which were analyzed using the PLS method. The results show that relative advantage, compatibility and observability are the determinants that influence the potential client decision to choose an Islamic bank. The results also reveal that the client gender has an impact on his uncertainty towards the bank products.

Keywords: Islamic bank; Selection criteria; Innovation diffusion theory; Morocco

1. Introduction

Islamic banks appeared in the beginning of the 1970s. In fact, the rise of oil prices during this period of time, lead to considerable savings in the Arabic oil producing countries. This money was invested in Islamic banks, which was the reason for those banks development. However in the early 2000s, Islamic banks appeared in some western countries like UK in 2004 followed by Germany, France and USA. This development contributed to the expansion of the Islamic financial industry operations (Godlewski et al., 2014; Hoque et al., 2018). In fact, the sector had known a growth rate of 6.9% and reached a total value of 2.19 billion dollars in 2018 (IFSB, 2019). The Islamic banking products specificity is interest prohibition, which makes those banks less risky because they don't participate to any risky financial operations (Ackermann & Jacobs, 2008; Jamshidi et al., 2014).

Through the past few years, the competition between Islamic and conventional bank had risen (Beck et al., 2013). This situation pushed the Islamic banks to introduce innovative financial products and services in order to attract new clients' portfolio (Jamshidi & Hussin, 2016; Sun et al., 2012). According to Estiri et al (2011), given that the banking sector is very competitive, banks should always study the changes on clients' behavior and preferences.

In Morocco, the first Islamic banking products were introduced in 2007 by a law made by the Moroccan central bank. At this time, there were no Islamic bank and those products were available in the conventional banks by the name of "Alternative products"¹. However, at the time, only "Dar assafa" (Attijari Wafa Bank subsidiary) was authorized by the central bank to be the first financial organization to develop and sell Islamic financial products. This organization had offered one product called "Murabaha" which is a loan for real estate acquisition, but this one failed to catch the potential client's interest because of its higher cost compared to the equivalent product in the conventional banks. The new Moroccan bank law² in 2014 represented the legal framework to the Islamic banks opening in Morocco. However, the first five Islamic banks were able to settle in the Moroccan financial market in 2017.

The evolution of the Islamic banks activity in the past three years in Morocco was positive. In fact, the total of assets rose from 452 million dirhams in 2017 to 12151 million dirhams in 2019 (Bank al Maghrib, 2019). In the same year, the banks agencies network had known the opening of 33 new agencies through the country to face the growing demand in this market (Bank al

¹ Murabaha, Musharaka & Ijara

² Central Bank law number 103.12

Maghrib, 2019). In general, according to Moroccan central bank, financing granted by Islamic banks increased by 50% to more than 18.51 billion DH in October 2021. These financings are therefore divided between real estate (15.71 billion DH), consumption (1.13 billion DH), equipment (1.53 billion DH) and cash (35 MDH) (BAM, 2021).

Furthermore, it appears that the prominence of Islamic banks, as new entrants in the Moroccan financial market, enables the development of a better understanding of how their potential clients perceive the Islamic financial products and how they choose to be Islamic bank clients or switch from conventional banking. In fact, Amin et al., (2013) emphasize the role market study plays in performing a good marketing strategy and to using appropriate marketing tools to create a good relationship with clients.

(Karbhari et al., 2004) advance that the Islamic banks function in different business environment: countries adopting Islamic laws, like Iran and KSA; those that function in non-Muslim countries like UK and USA and those that operate in Muslim countries with conventional banks, which is the case of Morocco. Consequently, it is more important for banks marketers to know exactly what their target selection criteria are, in order to perform marketing strategies and actions to get new clients.

The Islamic bank selection criteria was the subject of many studies conducted in many countries like in Malaysia (Abduh & Azmi Omar, 2012; Dusuki & Abdullah, 2007); Pakistan (Hamid & Masood, 2011; Khuram & Awan, 2011; Subhani et al., 2012); United Arab Emirates (Sayani & Miniaoui, 2013; Shome et al., 2018); Bangladesh (Iqbal et al., 2018; Rashid & Hassan, 2009); in Mauritius (Abduh et al., 2018); and in Jordan (Ramadan, 2013). These studies results made the literature more rich and various, depending on the cultural context and business environment. However, it doesn't apply to other countries because of the context divergence (Precious C. Ezeh et al., 2020).

Numerous studies in Morocco have examined Islamic bank choice in the mixt context (Muslim country with conventional banks). For examples, Essarhiri & Vol, (2021) studied the factors that influence the Islamic bank products purchase intentions; Allouch, (2021) studied the choose criteria; Amedjar, (2021) studied the companies choosing criteria for Islamic financial solutions; Boulahrir, (2018) conducted research on client expectations and Zarouali, (2017) on Islamic bank image attractiveness.

For Moroccan clients who are used to conventional banks, the opening of Islamic banks was an innovation that offers new kind of financial products that respect the principles of the Islamic

religion. Since that time, Moroccan people start having the opportunity to choose between conventional or Islamic banks.

Through this work, we aim to identify the criteria relied upon by the Moroccan potential clients in choosing Islamic bank services and products. For this purpose, we will adopt the Rogers, (2003) innovation theory. On one hand, this choice was made for two reasons. In fact, this theory is commonly used in similar studies about the innovation diffusion especially for the adoption of Islamic banks services (El Mallouli & Sassi, 2022; Thambiah et al., 2013; Yahaya et al., 2016; Yusof., 1999), and on the second hand, this kind of financial organizations are in their activity beginning, which make it an innovation for Moroccan clients in the financial market.

In order to accomplish our study, we conducted an exploratory study by performing a survey among potential Islamic banks' clients. This survey is based on a questionnaire electronically administered to a sample of 200 potential clients. The questionnaire is composed by different items and scales related to the attributes of Islamic banks adoption. Also, it contains many sociodemographic and economic characteristics for the target population. The collected data allowed us to make and estimate a research model using linear structural relationships method. To answer our problem, we divided this work into six sections: we will start with an introduction, followed by a literature review. The third part will be devoted to the methodology adopted, while the fourth and fifth sections will consist of a description of the results obtained, followed by a discussion. The final section will be a conclusion of our work.

2. Theoretical background

In Our theoretical background, we are going to focus on the concepts that impact the clients' decision to choose an Islamic bank. For that, we are going to mobilize the innovation diffusion theory (Rogers, 2003). In fact, this theory is commonly used in the case of an innovation adoption. The first version of this theory was published by Rogers in 1962. After that many updated versions were developed especially in 1999 and 2003.

In fact, Rogers (2003)' theory suggests different concepts to explain the individual adoption and collectively diffusion based on multiple studies crossing fields of psychology, education, sociology, geography, business and others (Precious Chikezie Ezeh & Nkamnebe, 2018). According to Rogers (2003), innovation adoption is the customers' decision to choose the use of an innovation or product. The main strength of this theory is the fact that it has affected many

other theories of adoption and diffusion (Boyne et al., 2005; Deffuant et al., 2005; Straub, 2009; Venkatesh, Viswanath, Michael G. Morris, Gordon B. Davis, 2003)

Accordingly, Rogers' theory has determined five characteristics that affect the individual adoption of an innovation, namely: Compatibility, Observability, Complexity, Relative advantage, and Trialability (Verhoef & Thambiah Langerak, 2001).

2.1. Relative advantage

According to Rogers (2003), the relative advantage represents the proportion for the adopters of how the new innovation is better than the previous idea. In fact, the relative advantage is an important characteristic for the potential adopters to make a decision concerning a new innovation (Thambiah et al., 2011). That is because it allows the adopters to examine the innovation and its benefits (Thambiah et al., 2013).

Many studies demonstrated the importance of this aspect in the decision process of the Islamic banks adoption (M. Ali & Puah, 2017; Q. Ali et al., 2018; Duan et al., 2010; Eriksson et al., 2008; Gerrard & Barton Cunningham, 2003; Jamshidi & Hussin, 2016; Kaabachi, 2012; Sun et al., 2012). Consequently, we assume the following hypothesis:

H1: The relative advantage affects positively the Islamic bank adoption decision.

2.2. Compatibility

The compatibility refers to the degree of to an innovation respects current values, beliefs and past experience of potential adopters (Rogers, 2003). In fact, Arts et al., (2011) demonstrates how the customer adoption intention of a product is strongly affected by compatibility. Furthermore, Sherry, (1997) confirm that a lack of this aspect lead to the innovation reject. However, Flight et al., (2011) explained that if customers perceive an innovation as suitable for their lifestyle, then it would be compatible on a personal level. Many studies about the compatibility confirm a positive link between compatibility and the innovation adoption decision (M. Ali & Puah, 2017; Q. Ali et al., 2018; Kaabachi, 2012; Obeid & Kaabachi, 2016). The following propositions thus ensue:

H2: The Compatibility positively impacts the Islamic bank adoption decision.

2.3. Complexity

Rogers (2003) defines complexity as the difficulty perception of an innovation to be understand and used. In fact, the complexity is the characteristic that makes the innovation hard to understand and to use, which would be an obstacle for the innovation adoption.

The complexity concept was studied and measured in relation to clients' perceptions about the ease use of the innovation attributes (Gerrard & Barton Cunningham, 2003; Thambiah et al., 2013). Indeed, complexity of an Islamic bank' product can function as a drag for its successful adoption. It seems that complexity is a key determinant of adoption intention (Lean et al., 2009).

Furthermore, many studies have shown the negative effect between complexity of Islamic banks products and their adoption rate (M. Ali & Puaah, 2017; Kaabachi, 2012; ROGERS, 2003; Sanni et al., 2013; Thambiah et al., 2010). Which makes us propose the following hypothesis:
H3: Complexity negatively impacts the Islamic bank adoption decision.

2.4. Trialability

Trialability was defined as the fact that an innovation could be experimented by people before its adoption in a limited basis (Carayannis & Turner, 2006; Flight et al., 2011; Rogers, 2003). The trialability reduce the doubt and enhances the innovation potential adopters trust (Lin and Chen, 2012). According to Rogers (2003), during the trialability interfere the rectification and improvement process, called reinvention. Otherwise, many studies has confirmed the link between trialability and intention to use (Anuar et al., 2012) and attitude toward use (Chen et al., 2009).

However, in the case of a bank, the trialability seems to be absent because banks doesn't give the potential clients the possibility to try their product in order to decide if they are going to adopt them or not(Gerrard & Cunningham, 1997; Kaabachi, 2012; Metawa & Almosawi, 1998; Thambiah, 2012; Yusof., 1999). That's why some previous studies (Gerrard & Cunningham, 1997; Kaabachi, 2012; Thambiah, 2012; Yusof., 1999) suggest to replace « Trialability » by « Perceived uncertainty ». In fact, the uncertainty is related to trust, reliability and the perceived risk (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018; Rogers, 2003). For this reason, we are going to replace trialability by perceived uncertainty in our study, to explain the adoption of the Islamic banks. We assume that:

H4: Uncertainty negatively impacts the Islamic bank adoption decision.

2.5. Observability

Rogers (2003) has explained observability as the capacity to see the innovation adoption results, those ones could be financial or not. In fact, observability enhance the visibility of the adoption decision, which encourage potential adopters to keep the innovation definitively (Lin & Chen, 2012). Furthermore, observability leads to client loyalty and positive behavior toward the innovation like the positive word of mouth and product or service recommendation

(Lichtenstein & Williamson, 2006). Otherwise, Lin and Chen (2012) adopt the idea that if an organization or an individual observe their partners taking advantage from an innovation, this will encourage them to do the same. Moreover, Yusof (1999) emphasize in his study that for Muslim clients, it will be easier to give feedback and to evaluate the Islamic banks products to other potential clients. Which will influence their attitude toward the use of Islamic banks products and services.

Many studies (Thambiah et al., 2010; M. Ali and Puah, 2017; Q. Ali et al., 2018) have confirmed the positive impact of observability on an innovation adoption. According to this, we will assume the following hypothesis:

H5: Observability positively impacts the Islamic Banks adoption.

2.6. Customer awareness

The adoption of an Islamic bank would not be possible without knowing the potential clients knowing about it. That's why Kotler and Armstrong (2018) had explained that a product adoption by a potential client start with the knowledge of its availability in the market. This knowledge happens when the potential client is exposed to the innovation and start understanding how it operates (Kasim & Wickens, 2020). The awareness was evaluated through familiarity with the Islamic banks principles, as the prohibition of interest, respect of Sharia laws, the principle of sharing profits and losses, Islamic banking products, etc. (Flight et al., 2011).

Many studies (Haron et al., 1994; Gerrard and Cunningham, 1997; Marimuthu et al., 2010; Saiti, 2015) took into consideration the customer awareness as a variable to explain an innovation adoption. That's because being knowledgeable of new product or service has an impact on the customers' decision to adopt or reject it (Kasim & Wickens, 2020; Shabbir, 2010). Which allow us to assume that:

H6: Customer awareness positively impacts Islamic bank adoption.

Finally, according to the literature, we made a research model which is presented as follow:

Figure N°1: conceptual research model

Source: authors

In order to enhance our models' strength, we added some control variables. Those variables are the potential client age, his income and his educational level. Our objective is to discover the impact of clients' sociodemographic characteristics on the Islamic banks adoption.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Instruments development

The questionnaire used by Thambiah (2012) to study the Islamic banks adoption in Malaysia, and the one used by Yahaya et al., (2016) to study Islamic financial products and services adoption in Nigeria were considered to elaborate our own questionnaire. In fact, some items were adopted to Moroccan context in order to facilitate their understanding by the Moroccan population.

Our questionnaire is composed by 4 sections. The first section contains questions about the potential client's profile. However, the other 3 sections focused on the studied concepts. Indeed, the second section is about the evaluation of the respondents' current banking practices. The third section provides an idea of the respondents' awareness of Islamic finance concepts and to know their perceptions toward Islamic banks. This section is divided into seven parts. Parts A and B are reserved for the respondents' responsiveness toward Islamic bank terms and characteristics, while parts C to G are reserved for the respondents' perceptions toward Islamic

financial products and services. The fourth and final section is about the evaluation of the adoption intention of the Islamic banks by the respondents.

3.2. Sampling and data collection

This paper tries to investigate the main influential factors of Islamic banks acceptance among bank customers in Morocco. Indeed, bank potential clients are the most appropriate target for this study, since the Islamic banks in Morocco are new entrant in the financial market. However, it is not possible to get any sampling frame because of banking regulations. Due to the fact that the Moroccan Financial Institutions law n°34-03 do not allow customer information to be revealed (Bank al Maghreb annual report, 2007), we chose a probability sampling method. In order to make our sample, we used a simple random technic. This choice was made for two reasons; first, we consider that any person who has the regulatory age to possess a bank account (either he already has a bank account or not) is considered by the Islamic banks as a potential client. Second, because we do not have access to a sampling frame (Leong et al., 2013; Zikmund et al., 2003).

To determine the sample size, we adopted Chin's (1998) recommendation. Indeed, Chin (1998) recommended that the sample size should be 10 times bigger than the structural relationships of the model. Therefore, in our case, the sample size should exceed 100 potential clients. In order to collect data, we were forced du to pandemic restrictions to administer the questionnaire using social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp) and emails. At the end, we stopped the data collection based on the saturation effect (Hennink & Kaiser, 2021). Finally, we collected 180 questionnaires ready to use.

3.3. Data analysis

To analyze the data, we used structural equation modeling (SEM). This approach is a statistical method to estimate the proposed research model. This choice is due to the objective of the study. In fact, we are looking to determine the factors that influence the potential client's choice toward the Islamic banks. This makes our study predictive of a future behavior. In view of that, many researchers recommend partial least square algorithm (PLS) for this kind of study (Henseler et al., 2015), for its strong predictive strength compared to other SEM approaches (Stan & Saporta, 2005). According to Byrne (2010), this method allows to test the hypothesis that refers to a structural theory.

In this regard, the research model is estimated using smart PLS v3 and SPSS v23 for some basic statistics and exploratory analysis.

4. Results

4.1. Data screening

To describe our results, we are going to start with the sample demographic characteristics (Gender; Age; Income; Educational level; Employment). Also, the possession or not of a banking account either in an Islamic bank or in a conventional one. In fact, the results show that our sample is composed by 58.9 per cent males and 40 per cent females. In term of age, young people aged between 26 Yo and 33 Yo represent the majority of the studied population (35 per cent), followed by people aged between 34 Yo and 40 Yo (23.3 per cent) and seniors aged between 41 Yo and 50 Yo (21.7 per cent).

For the educational level, most of our respondents have a master degree (48 per cent) followed by bachelor degree holders (38 per cent) and PhD holders (16 per cent). Concerning the employment, the distribution of the sample was 60 per cent government employees, 13.9 per cent students and 11.7 per cent private sectors employee. At the end, the sample distribution according to the income shows that the majority of the sample has an income bigger than 8000 Dhs per month (53 per cent). Finally, results show that 96 per cent of the respondents have a bank account. The results are summarized in the table 1.

Table N°1: The sample demographic characteristics

Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	106	59
Female	74	41
<i>Age</i>		
18 – 25	17	9,4
26 – 33	63	35,0
34 – 40	42	23,3
41 – 50	39	21,7
Above 50	19	10,6
<i>Educational level</i>		
Baccalaureate	5	2,77
Bachelor	58	32,22
Master	88	48,88
PhD	29	16,11
<i>Employment</i>		
Craftsman	2	1,2
Manager	11	6,1
Employee	21	11,7
Student	25	13,9
State employee	108	60
Factory worker	2	1,1

Liberal profession	7	3.88
Unemployed	4	2.2
Monthly income		
Less than 2.000 Dhs	8	4.4
2.000 – 3.999 Dhs	21	11.7
4.000 – 5.999 Dhs	6	3.3
6.000 – 7.999 Dhs	25	13.9
8.000 – 10.000 Dhs	26	14.4
Above 10.000 Dhs	36	20
Possession of a bank account		
Yes	172	96
No	8	4

4.2. Measurement model assessment

To analyze the model measurement, we used the Smart PLS 3v software that support the PLS algorithm (Terzis & Economides, 2011). To analyze the internal consistency, we used two indicators: composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. And for the convergent validity, we used the average of variance extracted (AVE) and Rho indexes (Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2018; Lacroux, 2009). Moreover, the discriminant validity was tested using Fornell–Larcker criterion and cross loadings (Chin, 2010; Hair Jr et al., 2014; Jamshidi & Hussin, 2016). The results are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Measurements reliability

	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Relative advantage	0,916	0,889
Compatibility	0,909	0,864
Complexity	0,924	0,840
Awareness	0,881	0,818
Uncertainty	0,864	0,771
Observability	0,818	0,700
Islamic banks adoption	0,934	0,917

According to Table 2, Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability of all constructs show satisfying results (0.70 and above), which, demonstrate the reliability of the constructs (Lacroux, 2009; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017).

Table 3. Convergent validity

	Rho A	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Relative advantage	0,896	0,647
Compatibility	0,894	0,718
Complexity	0,887	0,860
Awareness	0,825	0,651
Uncertainty	0,834	0,682
Observability	0,700	0,601
Islamic banks adoption	0,925	0,706

Concerning the convergent validity, Chin (2010) recommend that the AVE should be higher than the value of 0.50, which was achieved. Also for the Rho index, the table shows values that are bigger than 0.5 (Lacroux, 2009; Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2018) and indicates that the construct explain more than half of its indicators variance (Q. Ali et al., 2018; Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2011). Regarding this criteria results, the measurements convergent validity is confirmed.

About constructs' discriminant validity, we used Fornell–Larcker criterion and cross loading (Henseler et al., 2015). Results show for the cross loading test that each indicators loadings on its respective construct is higher than all of their cross loadings with other constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). Which proves the good discriminant validity of the studied concepts as shown in the table 4.

Table 4. Fornell–Larcker criterion (discriminant validity)

	Relative advantage	Compatibility	Complexity	Awareness	Uncertainty	Observability
Relative advantage	0,804					
Compatibility	0,718	0,847				
Complexity	0,146	0,002	0,927			
Awareness	0,747	0,733	0,055	0,807		
Uncertainty	-0,371	-0,293	0,170	-0,351	0,827	
Observability	0,556	0,642	0,091	0,592	-0,167	0,775

4.3. Internal model assessment

After testing the studied concepts measurement's reliability and validity, the next step is to evaluate the significance of the internal structural model. Indeed, we tested the internal model estimation by regression coefficient (R2) and path coefficients level and significance. Moreover, the total effect and the significance p are evaluated in the model assessment.

According to the results, the R2 value of Islamic banks adoption is 0.547, which proves that our model explains 54 per cent of the dependent variable (Islamic bank adoption). Indeed, it is a high value, especially in customer behavior studies (Hair et al., 2011). Furthermore, the results of hypothesis testing are exhibited in the following table.

Table 5. Hypothesis testing outcomes

Hypothesis	Path	Beta	p-value	Results
H1	Relative advantage → Islamic banks adoption	0,213	0,047*	Accepted
H2	Compatibility → Islamic banks adoption	0,279	0,004*	Accepted
H3	Complexity → Islamic banks adoption	0,077	0,279	Rejected
H4	Uncertainty → Islamic banks adoption	- 0,041	0,527	Rejected
H5	Observability → Islamic banks adoption	0,329	0,000**	Accepted
H6	Awareness → Islamic banks adoption	0,004	0,971	Rejected

Notes: *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$

According to table 5, the independent variables of relative advantage, compatibility and observability had significant big effect to explain the Islamic banks adoption. However, we found that complexity, uncertainty and awareness have a small non-significant effect on the Islamic banks' adoption.

In fact, when a potential client knows that the Islamic bank is better than the conventional bank, in term of financial products and services benefits (advantages), this will enhance the chance by 21 per cent ($\beta = 0.213^*$) to make him/her become a client of an Islamic bank. Also, if a client is convinced that the Islamic banks respects his values and beliefs, that will explain 27 percent ($\beta = 0.279^*$) of his/her choice for an Islamic bank. Furthermore, if the potential client see the innovation adoption results, either financial or not, this would explain his/her decision to be an

Islamic bank client by 32 per cent ($\beta=0.329^{**}$). Therefore, while H1, H2 et H5 of study are accepted, H3, H4 and H6 are rejected.

Moreover, we added some demographic variable to our research model in order to extend our analysis and explore those variables effect on the potential client adoption decision. The analysis results are presented in the following table:

Table 6. Significant demographic variables effect

Path	Beta	p-value
Male → Uncertainty	-0,152	0,049*
Female → Uncertainty	0,152	0,045*

Notes: *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$

The table shows a significant effect from the potential client gender toward the uncertainty. In fact, the perceived uncertainty is not the same for male and female potential clients. It appears clearly that males are less vigilant about the Islamic bank products perceived risk and reliability. However, female potential clients pay more attention to this factor and may not chose to be an Islamic bank client if it appears to them that the services and products doesn't fit their needs (quality and reliability) and respect their believes. Furthermore, we found that there is no significant effect between clients' income and educational level and the model variables.

5. Discussion

The main objective of this study was to study the factors that influence acceptance of Islamic banks' products and services by potential Moroccan clients. To achieve this objective, we used Rogers (2003)' characteristics for an innovation acceptance, namely, relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, observability and uncertainty. In view of the comparison between previous empirical research studies results and our study findings, we had noticed that:

Relative advantage has a positive impact on the Islamic banks' adoption. This result was confirmed by Rogers (2003), Eriksson et al., (2008) and Hsu et al., (2007). In fact, once the potential client believe that he/she is going to have a perceived positive relative advantage from the Islamic bank products and services, this will lead him/her to adopt the bank services. However, Thambiah (2012) found an opposite result in his study conducted in Malaysia.

Our study explains that there is a significant association between compatibility and intention to be an Islamic bank client. This confirms the results of Thambiah et al. (2012) study in which

compatibility found to be a robust factor influencing customer' Islamic banking services adoption. Indeed, this result proves that the Islamic bank is adequate to the Moroccan potential client's beliefs and values compared to their past bank choice. The same conclusion was found by Yusof (1999) and Gerrard and Cunningham (2003). In view of that, banks headquarters should match the products and services to the clients' lifestyle and beliefs in order to attract them and make a various portfolio.

Also, our study proved the positive link between Observability and Islamic Banks adoption. In fact, the observability of the Islamic bank adoption results has a positive impact on the potential clients' Islamic bank adoption. This result fit with Rogers (2003) and Thambiah (2012) findings. In fact, if a potential client observes the real advantage through the relationship between his/her surrounding environment (family; colleagues...) and the Islamic bank, this will push him/her to do the same. This situation should alert the Islamic banks managers to offer products and services that deliver a real advantage and not fake or same, or expensive products and services as conventional banks, to the clients. In fact, the opposite, it will drive away the customers. This situation is the actual case in Morocco because the Islamic financial products and services still expensive compared to those for conventional banks.

However, our study show that complexity, awareness and uncertainty have weak effect (doesn't exceed 7%) on the Islamic bank adoption. But this result is not significant statistically speaking. In fact, the study found that the complexity has small effect on the adoption intention of Islamic banks. This finding is the same as previous research that showed non-significant relationship between complexity and Islamic bank' adoption (Brown et al., 2003; Corrigan, 2012; Duan et al., 2010; Tan and Teo, 2000). Same for uncertainty and intention to adopt Islamic banks. Which confirms Anuar et al. (2012) and Hsu et al. (2007) studies. Finally, the awareness and as concluded by the study conducted by Thambiah (2012) in Malaysia, it is found that the awareness of potential customers in relation to participatory finance products and services does not significantly contribute to the adoption of these banks. Unlike the study conducted on online banking adoption (Gerrard & Cunningham, 2003), which concluded that consumer awareness is a relevant factor in online banking adoption intention.

6. Conclusion

In this research, we tried to determine the factors that lead a Moroccan potential client to adopt Islamic banks' products and services. Indeed, we used the Rogers (2003)' innovation diffusion theory to get the determinants of Islamic banks choice. Our study shows that relative advantage, compatibility and observability have a positive influence toward the potential client choice for Islamic banks services and products. However, we couldn't prove the influence of complexity, uncertainty and awareness toward the potential client adoption because the results were statistically non-significant. Furthermore, we found that the gender has an impact on uncertainty. Also, the uncertainty towards the Islamic banks products and services is more important for female than male.

Nevertheless, this research also has limitations. In fact, our model measures potential clients' perceptions in a specific time. It would be better to use longitudinal studies, because potential clients' attitudes and perceptions may change overtime. Furthermore, even if the sample size respects the scientific criteria, it still not enough to generalize the findings among all Moroccans. Moreover, the Islamic banking market in Morocco is a new market, so it will take time to know what marketing elements should be used to attract Moroccan potential clients globally.

In future studies, we should consider the regions culture especially criteria that influence the customer choice. In fact, we considered that the collected data is homogenous, which explain the use of PLS model may be unrealistic (Hair et al., 2011). However, in future studies we should consider multi group analyses to determine heterogeneity between customers segments. This idea was what we planned to do at the beginning, but the pandemic circumstances were an obstacle.

Despite everything, this study contributes to understand the Islamic banks adoption using Rogers (2003) theory. This kind of studies is rare in Morocco because the market is still in its beginning. At the end, this research is the beginning of the exploration of the Islamic financial products adoption in Morocco. Further analysis of the topic will be conducted studying real clients.

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